

ISic2982

I.Sicily inscription 2982

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

(?)

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Testa dell'Acqua (Mezzo Gregorio)

Provenance

Mezzo Gregorio, 12.5km south of Palazzolo, geo 36.97084, 14.95764

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palazzolo Acreide, Museo Iudica

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI175491

1. EK

2. TΩK

3. #⁷#⁷#⁷

4.

5. Ç [— —]

6. ṀACAC

7. ẸNKAP

8.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645335

PHI 175491

Bibliography

Orsi, P. 1931. Epigrafe cristiana di Palazzolo Acreide (Acrae). Contributo alla storia dell'altipiano acrese nell'antichità. *Rivista di Archeologia Cristiana*. 8: 287-299. At 296 = Orsi (1942) 211 fig.107

Pugliese Carratelli, G. 1956. Silloge dell' epigrafi acrensi. In Bernabó Brea, L. (eds.), *Akrai*. Catania. pp. 151-181. At no.58

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic2982. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4387863>